

1 **A temporo-spatial analysis of the neural correlates of extrinsic perceptual**
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4 **grouping in vision**

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47 **Running head:** Neural basis of extrinsic grouping

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Abstract

Principles of perceptual grouping can be divided into *intrinsic grouping cues*, which are based on built-in properties of the grouped elements (e.g., their shape, position, colour, etc.) like most of the classical Gestalt laws, and *extrinsic grouping principles*, based on relations between the discrete elements and other external stimuli that induce them to group (e.g., common region, connectedness). Several studies have explored the neural correlates of intrinsic grouping factors but, to our knowledge, no previous study has studied the neural correlates of extrinsic principles. The present study aimed to shed light on this issue by exploiting the high temporal resolution of event-related potentials (ERPs) and recent advances in source localization. Specifically, grouping by common region was compared with two comparison conditions, an intrinsic grouping (luminance similarity) and a uniform stimulus condition, in a perceptual discrimination task. We reported three main neural effects associated with grouping by common region. First, a posterior N210 component with a neural origin in the left extrastriate cortex was related to perceptual analysis of extrinsic elements inducing grouping and the formation of a visual group. Second, an enhanced posterior P280, which presumably reflects higher confidence decisions during response selection. Finally, a P550 originated in the right superior parietal cortex that seems to be associated with top-down suppression activity connected with the termination of the processing of the current trial. Overall, our results suggest that common region cues belong to the category of long latency grouping principles that mainly involve activity in extrastriate cortices.

Keywords: Perceptual grouping; extrinsic grouping; common region; ERP; LORETA.

1. Introduction

The world we perceive consists of objects and their interrelations coherently arranged in scenes. The human visual system arranges the retinal mosaic into structured images by means of internal processes of organization (Palmer, 1999). The study of perceptual organization was developed by Gestalt psychologists one century ago (see Wagemans et al., 2012, for a review). According to Max Wertheimer (1923), organization is basically composed of grouping and segregation processes. The classical Gestalt principles describe the stimulus factors that determine the visual grouping of discrete elements, including proximity, similarity, common fate, good continuation and closure (Wertheimer, 1923). In the last two decades, other principles of grouping have been proposed, such as common region (Palmer, 1992), element connectedness (Palmer and Rock, 1994a, 1994b), synchrony (Alais et al., 1998; Lee and Blake, 1999), regularity (van den Berg et al., 2011) and induced grouping (Vickery, 2008).

Most relevant to the present study, Palmer (1992, 1999) introduced a distinction between *intrinsic grouping principles*, which are based on built-in properties of the grouped elements (e.g., their shape, position, colour, etc.) like most of the classical Gestalt principles, and a new set of *extrinsic grouping principles* based on relations between the elements and other external elements that induce them to group. For example, identical elements equally spaced in a display tend to be grouped together when they are located within the same spatial region (i.e., grouping by common region proposed by Palmer, 1992) or when they are connected by lines (i.e., grouping by connectedness proposed by Palmer and Rock, 1994a, 1994b). The main goal of the present study was to examine the neural correlates of common region, a representative sample of the extrinsic grouping principles.

1 During the last century, there has been important progress in research on perceptual
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3 grouping in the context of vision science, mainly concerning the development of
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5 quantitative laws and measures of strength of classical grouping factors (for an
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7 extensive review on these issues, see Wagemans et al., 2012). More recently, several
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9 studies have been devoted to examining the temporal course and neural substrates of
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11 intrinsic perceptual grouping (see Sasaki, 2007). In contrast, the study of extrinsic
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13 grouping principles has received less attention. The results of several behavioural
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15 studies have suggested that they could constitute a different kind of principle, which
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17 operate differently from intrinsic principles (Palmer, 1992; Palmer and Beck, 2007).
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23 The evidence from behavioural studies devoted to intrinsic principles suggests that
24
25 different subtypes of grouping could have a different temporal course: grouping by
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27 proximity can be processed faster or earlier than grouping by similarity (Ben-Av and
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29 Sagi, 1995; Han and Humphreys, 1999; Han et al., 1999a,1999b); grouping by
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31 proximity is faster than grouping by good continuation (Kurylo, 1997); and grouping
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33 forming simple shapes (i.e., elements grouped by common lightness into columns or
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35 rods or into a shape that does not require segregation from other elements) is faster than
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37 grouping forming complex shapes (i.e., elements grouped by common lightness into a
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39 shape that requires segregation from other elements; Kimchi and Razpurker-Affeld,
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41 2004; Razpurker-Affeld and Kimchi, 2007).
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48 ERP studies also showed differences in the temporal course of the neural correlates
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50 underlying intrinsic grouping principles. Grouping by proximity was associated with a
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52 positive component over occipital electrodes that peaked between 100 and 120 ms after
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54 sensory stimulation. Similarly, contour integration by collinearity emerges from 130 ms
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56 after stimulus onset, as evidenced by the results from Machilsen et al. (2011). In
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1 contrast, grouping by similarity (in shape or colour) was linked to a negativity over
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3 occipito-temporal scalp regions occurring much later, around 300 ms (Han, 2004; Han
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5 and Humphreys, 2002; Han et al., 2001, 2002, 2005a; Mao et al., 2004). However, the
6
7 claim that grouping by proximity produces shorter latencies in ERP studies than
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9 grouping by similarity has been questioned by some authors (Kubovy and van den Berg,
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11 2008; Nikolaev et al., 2008), given that the subjective strength of grouping by proximity
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13 and similarity was not equated, or even measured, in the studies quoted above. Thus,
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15 controlling for grouping strength seems to be a crucial aspect to consider in future
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17 research in order to obtain more conclusive results. Another relevant result observed in
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19 several ERP studies is related to the asymmetric hemispheric distribution of the intrinsic
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21 grouping factors. Han et al. (2001, 2002) found a greater role for the right hemisphere in
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23 proximity but a greater left lateralization in similarity. An explanation has been
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25 proposed in terms of spatial filtering of visual images and the relative dominance of the
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27 left and right hemispheres in the processing of high and low spatial frequencies,
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29 respectively (Beck et al., 1987; Ginsburg, 1986). According to this view, similarity
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31 grouping would require applying a high-pass filter, mainly mediated by the left
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33 hemisphere, in order to detect the visual cues needed for clustering the local elements
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35 (colour, shape, size, etc.). In contrast, proximity grouping can be usually solved by an
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37 analysis of low spatial frequencies, which is associated with activity in the right
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39 hemisphere (but see Han et al., 2001, Experiment 2).

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41 Neuroimaging studies also showed a different neural substrate for grouping by
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43 proximity and by similarity, suggesting that the primary visual cortex (V1) may be
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45 involved in grouping by proximity but not in grouping by similarity, which seems to
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47 depend on activation of higher visual areas (Han, 2004; Han et al., 2005). Similarly,
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1 Altmann et al. (2003) found that Gabor patches grouped by collinearity generated
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3 greater activity in V1 than ungrouped Gabor patches. Finally, Wu et al. (2005) found
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5 that collinearity and proximity could share a common neural substrate in the primary
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7 visual cortex (see Sasaki, 2007, for a revision). In contrast, grouping by shape similarity
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9 has been associated with activation of higher areas such as the middle occipital and
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11 temporal cortices (Han et al., 2005a, 2005b). Also, activation within a shape-selective
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13 region, the lateral occipital complex (LOC), has been observed when participants had to
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15 respond to global shapes independently of the low-level visual cues (see Grill-Spector et
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17 al., 2001, for a review). In particular, perception of an object formed by grouping by
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19 motion (Fang et al., 2008; Ferber et al., 2003) or generating global shapes through
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21 grouping by collinearity (Altmann et al., 2003) seem to increase activation within this
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23 area.
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31 A key question is referred to the spatiotemporal characteristics of perceptual
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33 organization mechanisms in early and higher visual areas in the human brain (Kourtzi
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35 and Huberle, 2005). Especially, the role of feedback loops from higher areas to lower
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37 sensory regions is largely unknown. Animal studies have provided support for the
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39 presence of recurrent mechanisms mediating top-down effects in the integration of local
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41 elements into a global configuration (see Roelfsema, 2006, for a revision). In humans,
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43 however, the study of feedforward and feedback processes with only non-invasive
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45 methods is more challenging (de-Witt and Schwarzkopf, 2014; Kourtzi and Huberle,
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47 2005). Notably, a recent study including a simultaneous EEG-fMRI recording have
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49 provided precise evidence for the existence of a feedback loop from LOC to low-level
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51 retinotopic areas such as V1 during the processing of contour integration (Mijovic et al.,
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53 2014). Other studies have explored the top-down modulation of grouping associated
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1 with attention. Measuring fMRI and ERP activity, Han and co-workers found that the
2 calcarine cortex was involved in grouping by proximity but not in grouping by shape
3 similarity (Han et al., 2005a, 2005b). In addition, they reported that the relevance for the
4 task of stimulus arrays, as well as its locus, inside or outside of the attended area,
5 modulated neural substrates of perceptual grouping. Activity in the calcarine cortex
6 decreased when the elements fell outside of the attended area or when its relevance for
7 the tasks was low. Finally, recording ERPs from two patients with fronto-parietal
8 lesions and eight controls, Han and Humphreys (2007) found that the visuo-attentional
9 fronto-parietal network (Corbetta, 1998; Corbetta and Shulman, 2002; Gazzaley and
10 Nobre, 2014) was involved in the top-down modulation both of early and late intrinsic
11 grouping processes. Interestingly, their results suggested that the activity of the fronto-
12 parietal cortex was associated with enhanced initial sensory processes but, in contrast,
13 inhibited neural activity in the visual cortex at a later stage. In a similar direction, the
14 fMRI study of Seymour et al. (2008) revealed that the processing of different Gestalt
15 grouping cues (i.e. proximity and shape similarity) involved the activation of the
16 inferior parietal cortex, suggesting a top-down re-entrant modulation over the visual
17 areas.

18 In sum, the previous literature on intrinsic grouping suggests that different types of
19 grouping principles have divergent temporal courses and different neural origins. From
20 an integrative perspective, prior results could be grouped into two categories: (1) a short
21 latency grouping involving the activity of the striate cortex and linked to Gestalt
22 principles such as proximity or collinearity; and (2) a long latency grouping that
23 involves activation in the extrastriate and occipito-temporal areas associated with
24 similarity grouping (see Sasaki, 2007, for a similar account). In the first case, an early
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1 representation of spatial clustering of local elements based on their proximity or a
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3 detection of collinearity by linking responses of V1-cells aligned across space (but with
4
5 similar orientation tuning) may be mainly supported by the striate cortex. In contrast,
6
7 similarity grouping entails processing of more complex visual features (e.g., colour,
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9 shape, luminance, size, etc.) acting as parsing cues as a prerequisite to create a global
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11 pattern. Thus, higher-order visual areas specialized in the analysis of different visual
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13 characteristics seem to be implicated in grouping based on similarity.
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19 Although behavioural evidence has shown that intrinsic and extrinsic principles may
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21 operate based on different mechanisms, there are no previous studies devoted to
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23 investigating the neural substrates of extrinsic grouping principles. In the current study,
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25 we intended to perform an initial characterization of the processes and neural correlates
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27 underlying extrinsic grouping with a focus on perceptual grouping by common region.
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29 For this purpose, we included two comparison conditions. First, an intrinsic-grouping
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31 condition with the aim of differentiating between extrinsic and intrinsic cues (i.e.
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33 grouping by luminance similarity). The second condition consisted of a non-grouped
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35 uniform display with the same local elements included in both the experimental (i.e.
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37 common region cue) and the intrinsic-grouping comparison conditions but without any
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39 particular configuration. This condition allows differentiating grouping by common
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41 region from a no grouping display. There were two reasons for selecting luminance
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43 similarity as intrinsic grouping cue: (1) the manipulation of luminance similarity does
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45 not alter the spatial relationships between discrete elements to be grouped, so that the
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47 stimulus conditions are more comparable with common region, and (2) luminance
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49 similarity is easy to manipulate quantitatively (unlike shape similarity, for instance), a
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51 necessary condition to equate the subjective strength of the two grouping principles
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1 used in our study. We made use of similar displays as Luna and Montoro (2011) and
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3 Montoro and Luna (2015), composed by an array of seven elements, which have
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5 demonstrated to be very useful to study common region grouping cues. As a first step,
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7 we conducted preliminary behavioural experiments to select the appropriate stimuli in
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9 order to ensure that grouping strength was equated, as recommended by Kubovy and
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11 van den Berg (2008) and Nikolaev et al. (2008). Previous studies have showed that the
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13 phenomenological report paradigm is a sensitive tool for measuring the strength of
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15 perceptual grouping in behavioural studies (Gepshtein and Kubovy, 2005; Kubovy et
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17 al., 1998), as well as in ERPs research (Nikolaev et al., 2008). Secondly, we recorded
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19 ERPs from participants who paid attention to a central target of an array of seven
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21 elements and indicate whether this central element was included in a uniform, left-side
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23 grouped or right-side grouped display. Temporo-spatial principal component analysis
24
25 (PCA) and standardized low resolution brain electromagnetic tomography (sLORETA;
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27 Pascual-Marqui, 2002) were performed to better distinguish the processing stages and
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29 the brain areas involved in extrinsic grouping. PCA is a data-driven method that has
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31 shown to be a powerful approach to isolate ERP components across time course
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33 (temporal PCA) and scalp recording sites (spatial PCA). Considering that there is no
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35 previous study on brain correlates of extrinsic grouping, a two-step PCA might be a
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37 suitable tool for an initial approach to the neural processes underlying the common
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39 region principle. sLORETA is a 3D, discrete linear solution for the EEG inverse
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41 problem (i.e., the computation of the electric sources from surface data, Pascual-Marqui,
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43 2002).

44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 **2. Material and methods**

57 58 **2.1. Behavioural preexperiment**

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1 The main aim of this behavioural experiment was to select stimuli for luminance
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3 similarity and common region conditions that were equated in their subjective strength
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5 of grouping. Additionally, we also tested several stimulus exposure durations and the
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7 response set that would be used in the main experiment. Fifteen undergraduate students
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9 from the UNED (twelve females; age range = 26-56 years, Mean = 36.17, *SD* = 7.95)
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11 participated in this experiment and received course credits for their participation. Based
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13 on previous behavioural studies assessing strength of grouping (Luna and Montoro,
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15 2011; Quinlan and Wilton, 1998), a set of forty-four different displays were designed.
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17 Each display was made up of seven elements arranged in a row; the central element was
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19 the target. The other six elements were organized into two cohorts (right or left, made
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21 up of three elements flanking the target). The shapes used were squares (10 mm x 10
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23 mm) and circles (10 mm in diameter), which subtended 1.0 deg at a viewing distance of
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25 57 cm. The distance between the elements was 2.5 mm. The shapes were filled with two
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27 values of luminance (220 and 148 RGB; 48 and 20 cd/m²). Two horizontal parallel bars
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29 serving as common region cues; they had an intermediate value of luminance (184
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31 RGB; 31.4 cd/m²) between the other two filling luminances. The exposure duration of
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33 the stimuli could be 53, 200 or 347 ms. Each trial had two sequential stages. Firstly,
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35 participants had to pay attention to the central element of a display composed of seven
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37 geometric shapes and indicate whether this central element was included in a uniform,
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39 left-side grouped or right-side grouped display, by pressing down, left or right keys,
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41 respectively, of the arrow keys of the keyboard, using the middle, index and third
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43 fingers of the right hand as fast as possible. After responding, participants had to rate
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45 the degree to which the target was grouped with either the right or the left flanking
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47 element on a 4-point rating scale by pressing the top number keys with the left hand.
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49 The Escape key was available for stimuli grouped neither with the left nor with the right
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1 cohort, or in case of an error in the previous stage. The grouping strength ratings
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3 allowed us to select displays for luminance similarity and common region conditions
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5 with a similar subjective strength of grouping, which made up the set of stimuli for the
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7 electrophysiological experiment (see Fig. 1). The selected stimuli for luminance
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9 similarity and common region conditions showed a mean rating of 3.26 ($SD = 0.60$) and
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11 3.31 ($SD = 0.66$), respectively. A paired-samples t -test confirmed the similarity in
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13 strength of grouping between both conditions, $t(14) = 0.580$, $p = .571$. Moreover, the
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15 results showed no significant differences between the three exposure duration
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17 conditions either on accuracy, reaction time (RT), or grouping strength scores (all $F_s <$
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26 **2.2. ERP study**

27 **2.2.1. Participants**

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29 Twenty-four students (seventeen females) from the *Universidad Complutense de*
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31 *Madrid*, between 18 and 34 years of age (Mean = 22.08, $SD = 4.4$), voluntarily
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33 participated in this study. All of them reported normal or corrected-to-normal visual
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35 acuity, and gave their informed consent to participate in the study. The experiment was
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37 conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines of the local committee and conformed
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39 with the Declaration of Helsinki.
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46 **2.2.2. Stimuli and apparatus**

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48 According to the results of the behavioural preexperiment, twelve displays were
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50 selected (see Fig. 1) from the original collection of stimuli: four for each condition
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52 (common region, luminance and non-grouping) with grouping conditions equated in
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54 their subjective strength of grouping. In the uniform stimuli, it was not possible to group
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56 the central target with the elements on the right or on the left by means of any grouping
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1 principle, given that all the elements in the display formed a homogeneous group. In the
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3 common region displays, the central target could be grouped either with elements on the
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5 right or on the left side only by means of a common region cue. In the luminance
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7 similarity displays, the central target could be grouped either with elements on the right
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9 or on the left based on a luminance similarity cue exclusively. The three stimulus
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11 conditions were composed of the same local elements, namely solid squares with two
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13 different values of luminance (see above “*Behavioural preexperiment*” section). Two of
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15 the four uniform stimuli included horizontal parallel bars like those used as extrinsic
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17 grouping cues in the common region condition but covering all the elements. The other
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19 two uniform displays were composed of seven iso-luminant elements with no other
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21 element like luminance similarity displays. The luminance similarity stimuli combined
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23 two values of luminance in each display to group the central target with the right or left
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25 cohort of elements. All the 2 x 2 combinations between the luminance values and
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27 right/left cohorts were made. The common region displays included two horizontal bars
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29 covering four of seven elements to group the central target with the right or left cohort
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31 of elements. Again, all the 2 x 2 combinations between the luminance values and
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33 right/left cohort were made.

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35 The stimuli were displayed on a 19-inch LCD-LED Samsung 943N colour monitor with
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37 a 75-Hz refresh rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio, and a resolution of 1024 x 768 controlled by a
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39 computer running E-Prime 2.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996-2002).
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41 Viewing distance was approximately 57 cm.

42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 **2.2.3. Procedure and design**

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56 Each trial started with a cross-shape fixation mark at the centre of the screen; 1000 ms
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58 later, a stimulus was displayed for 200 ms and replaced by a blank screen that remained
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1 until response. Participants had to pay attention to the central element of a display
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3 composed of seven geometric shapes and indicate whether this central element was part
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5 of a uniform, left-side grouped or right-side grouped display, independently of the
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7 specific grouping cue applied, by pressing down, left or right keys, respectively, of the
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9 arrow keys of the keyboard, using the middle, index and third fingers of the right hand
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11 as fast as possible. There was an intertrial pause of 800 ms (see Fig. 2). A practise block
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13 with 72 trials and five experimental blocks consisting of 72 trials each, for a total of 360
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15 experimental trials (120 trials for each experimental condition), were presented. The
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17 design included the within-subjects factor Stimulus type consisting of three conditions:
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19 (1) grouping by common region and two comparison conditions, i.e. (2) no-grouping
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21 and (3) grouping by luminance similarity.
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28 **2.2.4. Recording and pre-processing**

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30 Electroencephalogram (EEG) activity was recorded from 62 electrode locations
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32 homogeneously distributed over the entire scalp (Quick-Cap, Neuroscan, Inc., USA).
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34 All electrodes were referenced to the linked mastoids. Bipolar horizontal and vertical
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36 electrooculograms (EOGs) were recorded to monitor eye movements and blinks.
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38 Electrode impedances were kept below 5 k Ω . Recordings were amplified using
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40 Neuroscan SynAmps amplifiers, continuously digitized at sample rate of 1000 Hz and
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42 filtered on-line with a frequency band-pass of 0.1-100 Hz.
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50 Data were processed off-line using the EEGLAB v.12.01 toolbox (Delorme and
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52 Makeig, 2004) implemented in MATLAB (Mathworks, Inc.). Recordings were down-
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54 sampled to 500 Hz and filtered between 0.3 and 30 Hz, using a basic FIR filter (12
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56 dB/oct. roll-off). The continuous EEG was epoched from 200 ms before to 800 ms after
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58 stimulus presentation. Baseline correction was made using the 200 ms period prior to
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1 the onset of each trial. Only correct-response epochs were further analyzed. Prior to
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3 artefact correction procedures, epochs in which recordings at any channel exceeded
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5 $\pm 150 \mu\text{V}$ were automatically discarded. Independent Component Analysis (ICA) was
6
7 then used to remove ocular and other artefacts from individual EEG data sets (see a
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9 description of this procedure and its advantages over traditional regression/covariance
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11 methods in Jung et al., 2000). Artefact-related ICs were first identified using ADJUST
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13 (Mognon et al., 2011) and then carefully inspected visually. ADJUST is an automatic,
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15 validated method for detecting artefacted ICs based on the simultaneous use of spatial
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17 and temporal features (for further details, see Mognon et al., 2011). After the ICA-based
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19 removing process, visual inspection of individual EEG epochs was also conducted. If
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21 any further artefact was present, the corresponding trial was discarded. This artefact
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23 rejection procedure led to the average admission of 99.96 ($SD = 11.48$) in no-grouping
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25 trials, 96.75 (13.47) in luminance similarity trials, and 100.75 (10.67) in common region
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27 trials. Grand averages were computed in all subjects separately for each condition and
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29 electrode location.
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38 **[Insert Figure 1 about here]**
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43 **2.2.5. Data analysis**

44 **2.2.5.1. Behavioural analysis**

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47 Median RTs of correct responses and mean accuracy were submitted to separate
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49 analyses of variance (ANOVAs) with Stimulus type as within-subject factor (three
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51 levels: no-grouping, grouping by luminance similarity and grouping by common
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53 region). Significant main effects were further explored using Bonferroni-adjusted post-
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55 hoc tests. For the RT analysis, inaccurate responses (on average 3.4%) were excluded.
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2.2.5.2. Scalp ERP analysis

Detection and quantification of ERP components was carried out through a temporo-spatial PCA. This procedure has been shown to be an effective data-driven method for analyzing ERP data (Chapman and McCrary, 1995; Dien and Frishkoff, 2005). Although it has not been completely determined whether the spatial PCA or the temporal PCA should be performed first, a simulation study of ERP data suggests that the temporo-spatial produced improved results over the spatio-temporal sequence (Dien, 2010). Thus, considering results from this study and recent published guidelines for applying PCA to ERP datasets (Dien, 2012), a two-step temporo-spatial PCA was employed. Thus, a covariance-matrix-based temporal PCA (tPCA) was firstly used to disentangle ERP components over time. The main advantage of tPCA over conventional procedures based on a visual inspection of the recordings and on ‘temporal windows of interest’ is that it presents each ERP component separately and with its ‘clean’ shape, extracting and quantifying it free of the influences of adjacent or subjacent components. Indeed, the waveform recorded at a site on the head over a period of several hundreds of milliseconds represents a complex superposition of different overlapping electrical potentials. Such recordings can stymie visual inspection. In brief, tPCA computes the covariance between all ERP time points, which tends to be high between the time points involved in the same component, and low between those belonging to different components. The solution is therefore a set of factors made up of highly covarying time points, which ideally correspond to ERP components. A temporal factor score, the tPCA-derived parameter in which extracted temporal factors may be quantified, is linearly related to amplitude. The decision about the number of factors to select was based on a covariance-based Parallel Analysis (Horn, 1965; for further details on how

1 Parallel Analysis was implemented, see López-Martín et al., 2013). Retained factors
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3 were submitted to Promax rotation, as recommended (Dien, 2010).
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7 Once quantified in temporal terms, temporal factor scores were submitted to spatial
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9 PCA (sPCA) in order to decompose the scalp topography of each component into its
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11 main spatial regions. Whereas temporal PCA separates ERP components along time,
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13 sPCA distinguishes ERP components along space, each spatial factor ideally reflecting
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15 one of the concurrent neural processes underlying each temporal factor. This spatial
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17 decomposition is an advisable strategy prior to statistical contrast, because ERP
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19 components frequently behave differently in some scalp areas than they do in others
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21 (e.g., they present opposite polarity or react differently to experimental manipulations).
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23 Basically, each region or spatial factor is formed with the scalp points where recordings
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25 tend to covary. As a result, the shape of the sPCA-configured regions is functionally
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27 based, and scarcely resembles the shape of the geometrically configured regions defined
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29 by traditional procedures. Moreover, each spatial factor can be also be quantified
30
31 through the spatial factor score, a single parameter that reflects the amplitude of the
32
33 whole spatial factor. Also in this case, retained factors were submitted to Promax
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35 rotation.
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44 Finally, repeated-measures ANOVAs were performed on each temporo-spatial factor
45
46 extracted by PCA using Stimulus type (three levels: no-grouping, grouping by
47
48 luminance similarity, and grouping by common region) as within-subject factor.
49
50 Greenhouse-Geisser (GG) epsilon correction was applied to adjust the degrees of
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52 freedom of the F-ratios. Significant main effects were further explored using
53
54 Bonferroni-adjusted post-hoc tests. Effect sizes were computed using the partial eta-
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1 square (η_p^2) method. All statistical analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics
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3
4 (version 20).
5
6

7 **2.2.5.3. Source localization analysis**

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9 To three-dimensionally locate the cortical regions that were sensitive to the
10 experimental effects observed at the scalp level, standardized low-resolution brain
11 electromagnetic tomography (sLORETA; Pascual-Marqui, 2002) was employed.
12 sLORETA is a 3D, discrete linear solution for the EEG inverse problem. Although, in
13 general, solutions provided by EEG-based source-location algorithms should be
14 interpreted with caution due to their potential error margins, LORETA solutions have
15 shown significant correspondence with those provided by hemodynamic procedures in
16 the same tasks (Dierks et al., 2000; Mulert et al., 2004; Vitacco et al., 2002). Moreover,
17 the use of tPCA-derived factor scores (which leads to more accurate source-localization
18 analyses: Carretié et al., 2004, Dien et al., 2003; Dien, 2010) instead of direct voltages
19 contributes to reducing this error margin. In its current version, sLORETA computes the
20 standardized current density at each of 6239 voxels mainly localized in the cortical gray
21 matter of the digitized Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) standard brain.
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42 Specifically, three-dimensional current-density estimates for each ERP component (as
43 defined by tPCA) were computed for each subject and each condition. Subsequently,
44 the voxel-based whole-brain sLORETA-images (6239 voxels at a spatial resolution of 5
45 mm) were compared between experimental conditions, using the sLORETA built-in
46 voxelwise randomization tests (5000 permutations) based on statistical non-parametric
47 mapping (SnPM). As explained by Nichols and Holmes (2002), the non-parametric
48 methodology inherently avoids multiple comparison-derived problems and does not
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1 require any assumption of Gaussianity. Voxels that showed significant differences
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3 between conditions were located in anatomical regions and Brodmann areas (BAs).
4
5

6 7 **3. Results**

8 9 10 **3.1. Behavioural data**

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12
13 Median RTs and mean accuracy (hit rates) as a function of Stimulus type are reported in
14
15 Table 1. Hit rates varied between 90 and 100%. The ANOVA on accuracy revealed a
16
17 significant effect of Stimulus type, $F(2, 46) = 19.3$, $MSe = .001$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .46$.
18
19 Post-hoc comparisons using Bonferroni correction showed that responses to luminance
20
21 similarity condition were less accurate than to no-grouping and common region (both ps
22
23 $< .01$). There was no difference between no-grouping and common region conditions (p
24
25 $> .10$).
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30
31 The ANOVA on RT showed a significant effect of Stimulus type, $F(2, 46) = 24.38$, MSe
32
33 $= 840.1$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .52$, indicating that RTs in common region stimuli were reliably
34
35 shorter (501 ms) than those in no-grouping (543 ms) and luminance similarity (559 ms)
36
37 displays (both $ps < .01$, Bonferroni correction). There was no difference between no-
38
39 grouping and luminance similarity conditions ($p > .10$).
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44
45 **[Insert Table 1 about here]**
46

47 48 **3.2. ERP data**

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50
51 Figure 3 shows a selection of grand averages once the baseline value (pre-stimulus
52
53 recording) had been subtracted from each ERP. These grand averages correspond to
54
55 posterior and central electrode locations, where experimental effects (described later)
56
57 were clearly visible. As a consequence of the application of the tPCA using the Parallel
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59 Analysis as a criterion of the number of factors to retain, ten temporal factors were
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1 extracted from the ERPs (Figure 4). Subsequently, the sPCA decomposed each of these
2
3 ten temporal factors into three major spatial factors (Table 2; see also Figure 4).
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6
7 **[Insert Figure 3 and 4 about here]**
8

9
10 **[Insert Table 2 about here]**
11

12 Repeated-measures ANOVAs on these spatial factors with respect to Grouping (three
13 levels: No-grouping, Luminance similarity and Common region) were then performed.
14
15 The Bonferroni procedure was used to correct for Type I errors as a result of multiple
16 comparisons ($p = .05/30$ [.002]). Table 2 shows the results of these analyses. As can be
17 seen, the main effect of Grouping was significant in posterior and/or central regions of
18 temporal factors 1, 5, 6 and 8 (see also Figure 5). Factors peak-latency and topography
19 characteristics associated temporal Factor 5 (peaking at 210 ms) with the wave labelled
20 N210 in grand averages, Factor 6 (280 ms) with P280, Factor 1 (470 ms) with P470, and
21 Factor 8 (550 ms) with P550. These labels will be employed hereafter to make the
22 results easier to understand.
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37 As explained above, significant main effects were further explored using Bonferroni-
38 corrected post-hoc tests. Results from these pairwise post-hoc analyses are also
39 summarized in Table 2. Firstly, the posteriorly distributed N210 showed larger (more
40 negative) amplitude for common region than for luminance and no-grouping conditions.
41
42 The amplitude of this component did not differ between luminance and no-grouping
43 conditions. Secondly, both left and right posterior P280 displayed larger amplitudes for
44 common region than for luminance and no-grouping conditions. Again, no differences
45 were observed between luminance and no-grouping. Thirdly, the centrally distributed
46 P470 showed larger amplitudes in the no-grouping condition than in the grouping
47 conditions (i.e., luminance and common region). The amplitude of this component did
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1 not differ between luminance and common region conditions. Finally, both central and
2
3 posterior regions of P550 displayed smaller amplitudes for common region than for
4
5 luminance and no-grouping conditions. Central and posterior P550 amplitudes elicited
6
7 by luminance and no-grouping conditions did not statistically differ.
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10
11 **[Insert Figure 5 about here]**
12
13

14 **3.3. Source localization data**

15
16 The last analytical step consisted of localizing the cerebral regions that are responsible
17
18 for the experimental effects described above. To this end, three-dimensional current-
19
20 density estimates for N210, P280, P470 and P550 components (as defined by tPCA)
21
22 were computed for each subject and each condition using the sLORETA software
23
24 package. Subsequently, for each of these components, the voxel-based whole-brain
25
26 images (6239 voxels at a spatial resolution of 5 mm) were compared between conditions
27
28 using the sLORETA built-in voxelwise randomization tests (5000 permutations) based
29
30 on SnPM. Differences between conditions were observed during N210 and P550 time
31
32 ranges (Table 3). Specifically, greater N210-associated activation in the left extrastriate
33
34 visual cortex (BA 19) was found for common region than for no-grouping condition
35
36 (Figure 6). A marginal significance was also found between common region and
37
38 luminance conditions. Parallel to the results from scalp ERP analysis, N210-associated
39
40 neural activity did not differ between luminance and no-grouping conditions. With
41
42 respect to P550, greater activation in the right superior parietal lobe (BAs 5 and 7) was
43
44 observed for common region than for no-grouping and luminance conditions (Figure 6).
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46 P550-associated activation did not differ between luminance and no-grouping
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48 conditions. No activation differences between conditions were observed in P280 and
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50 P470 components.
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[Insert Figure 6 about here]

[Insert Table 3 about here]

4. Discussion

In the current study, we identified the neural correlates underlying extrinsic perceptual grouping by comparing the temporo-spatial dynamics involved in common region grouping with those of two comparison conditions: intrinsic grouping (i.e., luminance similarity) and no-grouping (i.e., uniform displays). To this aim, we ensured that the subjective strengths of both grouping cues were equated (see Kubovy and van den Berg, 2008; and Nikolaev et al., 2008) by means of preliminary pilot experiments that allowed us to select the suitable stimuli for the main experiment. Interestingly, faster and more accurate responses were observed for common region than luminance similarity cue, in spite of their similar subjective grouping strength. A discrepancy between objective and subjective measures has been also previously observed by Schmidt and Schmidt (2013), who studied the competition between intrinsic grouping principles using both subjective and objective (a primed flanker procedure) tasks and stimuli with similar grouping strength. They found that grouping by similarity in shape was processed more efficiently than grouping based on size or brightness similarity, even though all the grouping cues were equated in grouping strength. It may be assumed that equating different stimulus features for their subjective impression of grouping strength does not necessarily imply that the features are also equated in the visuomotor system (Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013, p. 19) since the different requirements of the tasks used could lead to dissociation in the results obtained.

The electrophysiological results indicated that common region and luminance elicited similar amplitude modulations in a centrally distributed P470 component compared to

1 the no-grouping condition. Activity in the same time-range and with a similar
2
3 topography has been previously related to perceptual grouping, response selection and
4
5 preparation processes when participants had to detect the global configuration of
6
7 triangles formed by Gabor patches (Nikolaev and van Leeuwen, 2004). Notably,
8
9 specific correlates of common region grouping were found at both behavioural and
10
11 neural levels. In particular, common region elicited faster responses than the two
12
13 comparison conditions and more accurate than luminance similarity. Grouping by
14
15 common region cues was also associated with amplitude modulations in a posterior
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17 N210 component—which was originated in left extrastriate cortices—, a posterior P280
18
19 and a central-posterior P550—which showed a neural origin in parietal region. We will
20
21 first focus on the discussion of these specific effects and subsequently, we will attempt
22
23 to integrate them all in a comprehensive framework that accounts for the tempo-
24
25 spatial course of the processes involved in perceptual grouping by common region.
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32 33 34 **4.1. Posterior N210**

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37 The first index of the higher saliency of the grouping operations based on common
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39 region cues was the modulation of an N210 component in posterior electrodes that
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41 originated in the left extrastriate visual cortex (BA 19). Enhanced amplitude of this
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43 component, as well as greater activity in the left extrastriate cortex, was observed for
44
45 common region compared to both comparison conditions. These findings contrast with
46
47 those reported in studies that were concerned with the mechanisms underlying short
48
49 latency grouping effects. In this regard, Han and collaborators observed that grouping
50
51 by proximity was linked to activity in the striate cortex/V1, particularly in the calcarine
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53 area (Han et al., 2001, 2002, 2004, 2005a). Interestingly, several previous ERP studies
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55 showed that activation within these areas occurred between 100 and 120 ms, as reflected
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1 by modulations of a positive component over occipital electrodes (Han et al., 2001,
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3
4 2002, 2004). In contrast, the brain correlates of common region reported in the current
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6 work may be related to the long latency effects reported in other grouping studies. In
7
8 this sense, Han et al. (2001) found that grouping by shape similarity was reflected by an
9
10 occipito-temporal negativity between 260 and 420 ms with left hemisphere dominance.
11
12 In a different study, grouping by colour similarity was associated with a left occipito-
13
14 temporal negative component between 180 and 380 ms (Han et al., 2002). Finally, the
15
16 results of an fMRI study showed greater activity in the right middle occipital and the
17
18 left temporal cortex associated with grouping by shape similarity compared to a no-
19
20 grouping condition (Han et al., 2005b). These findings may be helpful when trying to
21
22 interpret our effects in a tentatively manner. In the current study, the detection of the
23
24 contour delimiting a common region should be a previous step to the grouping based on
25
26 this extrinsic cue. Once the extrinsic element (the two horizontal bars) that induces
27
28 grouping is perceived, all the elements inside it will share the topological property of
29
30 being contained by a large surrounding contour. Thus, compared with more *direct*, early
31
32 grouping cues like proximity or collinearity, common region might depend on a
33
34 preliminary formation of the extrinsic object delimiting a region and, then, their
35
36 application to the local elements. The neural origin of the N210 in extrastriate cortices
37
38 support the configuration of the extrinsic contour as a preliminary because activity
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40 within this region seems to be involved in the perception of object features comparable
41
42 to shape similarity grouping (Han et al., 2005a, 2005b). Specifically, we observed BA
43
44 19 activation when stimuli were grouped by common region cues. The BA 19 partially
45
46 overlaps with the LOC, an area that is known to play a relevant role in shape perception
47
48 and contour integration (Grill-Spector et al., 2001). Interestingly, some studies have
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50 shown that global shapes generated by means of grouping by motion (Ferber et al.,
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1 2003) or collinearity (Altmann et al., 2003; Mijovic et al., 2014) also elicited activity in
2
3 the LOC. Resembling our results, Zhang et al. (2013) found a modulation of an N180-
4
5 280 component originated in the left LOC in a Müller-Lyer illusion task. Therefore, the
6
7 results of prior work suggest that, in the current study, the enhanced activity in BA19
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9 was associated to the detection of the extrinsic contour inducing grouping of discrete
10
11 elements into a global pattern. Although null findings should be always interpreted with
12
13 caution, our proposal fits the lack of differences in activation within this region between
14
15 luminance similarity—which is not based on shape attributes—and no-grouping
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17 conditions.
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23 This tentative interpretation would be compatible with the definition of common region
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25 as a sort of grouping by “similarity of containment”, as suggested by Wagemans et al.
26
27 (2012, p. 1181), and, consequently, related to other long latency grouping factors (e.g.
28
29 shape similarity) assuming that common region requires the perception of the
30
31 surrounding shape containing the local elements as a logical precondition.
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37 Another interesting finding of our study was the left lateralization of the extrastriate
38
39 activity underlying the N210 component. Several behavioural and ERP studies
40
41 supported a correspondence between the left and right hemispheres and the specialized
42
43 processing of high and low spatial frequencies, respectively (Han et al., 2001; Kitterle et
44
45 al., 1993; Sergent, 1987; Watten et al., 1998). From this viewpoint, the left lateralization
46
47 of the extrastriate activity found in our study could be interpreted as an index of the
48
49 operations involved in the analysis of higher spatial frequency information to
50
51 discriminate the external elements (i.e., the two parallel bars) that induce grouping by
52
53 common region.
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59 **4.2. Posterior P280**

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1 The initial negativity linked to common region cues was followed by an enhanced
2
3 positivity, peaking at 280 ms, with a posterior distribution over the scalp. Similar effects
4
5 have been found in previous studies that explored perceptual grouping by different
6
7 grouping principles (Han, 2004; Han et al., 2001). In particular, positive ERP effects
8
9 within this time window seem to reflect an integrative process linking perception to
10
11 action, which mediates operations that occur between the identification of the stimulus
12
13 and the selection of the response (Verleger et al., 2005; Squires et al., 1975). According
14
15 to this account, the larger amplitude of the P280 may be specifically associated with the
16
17 existence of differences in confidence in perceptual decisions when participants selected
18
19 one out of many possible courses of action (Han et al., 2001; Kerkhof and Uhlenbroek,
20
21 1981). In fact, there is recent evidence showing certainty-specific ERP activity around
22
23 300 ms that has been related to perceptual decision confidence when observers
24
25 discriminated global visual motion and rated their confidence in their judgment
26
27 (Zizlsperger et al., 2014). From this view, it could be assumed that prior higher
28
29 perceptual saliency indexed by the enhanced N210 amplitudes found in common region
30
31 relative to comparison conditions led to a more confident decision about grouping of the
32
33 target at a subsequent processing stage. This explanation fits our behavioural findings of
34
35 faster responses for common region than those to comparison conditions and more
36
37 accurate than luminance similarity, even if grouping strength was controlled in the
38
39 current study.
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49 **4.3. Central-posterior P550**

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52 The longest-latency ERP effect found in our study was a decrease in the amplitude of a
53
54 central-posterior P550 in common region compared to the comparison conditions. The
55
56 source-localization analysis pointed to the right superior parietal cortex (BAs 5 and 7)
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1 as the neural origin of this effect, showing a greater activation for common region
2
3 compared to luminance similarity and no-grouping conditions. It should be noted that
4
5 the latency of this component was very similar to the behavioural response provided by
6
7 the participants (see Table 1). This suggests that the P550 component may be a
8
9 reflection of mechanisms involved in the completion of the processing of the current
10
11 trial and the preparation for the processing of the next trial. Notably, the greater
12
13 activation of the superior parietal cortex for common region condition was reflected in
14
15 reduced P550 amplitudes. The activity of the visuo-attentional fronto-parietal network
16
17 may account for these findings (Corbetta, 1998; Corbetta and Shulman, 2002; Gazzaley
18
19 and Nobre, 2014). This network is involved in the top-down modulation both of early
20
21 and late grouping processes. In an ERP study including patients with parietal damage,
22
23 Han and Humphreys (2007) found that both short- and long-latency activities indexing
24
25 visual grouping in controls were absent or severely weakened in fronto-parietal
26
27 damaged patients. These authors concluded that the activity of the fronto-parietal cortex
28
29 enhances initial sensory processes and then suppresses activity in the visual cortex at a
30
31 later processing stage. Therefore, given the neural origin of the P550 in the superior
32
33 parietal cortex, we interpret this effect as an index of inhibitory modulations that are
34
35 under top-down control. In particular, once attention has facilitated processes devoted to
36
37 perceptual organization by means of extrinsic grouping principles, an active suppression
38
39 mechanism seems to operate in order to disengage attention from perceptual grouping
40
41 cues involved in the current trial, especially if different grouping principles may be
42
43 applied to an upcoming event. Thus, the higher activation of the right superior parietal
44
45 cortex linked to common region may be related to a clearer, more emphatic resolution to
46
47 cancel the current trial and to move on to the next one. A similar mechanism has been
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49 postulated in the domain of spatial attention. Specifically, it has been shown that
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1 following the allocation of attentional resources to a given spatial location, an active
2
3 suppression process disengages attention from the previously attended location,
4
5 facilitating the subsequent re-orienting of attention to a new target (Sawaki and Luck,
6
7 2013; Sawaki et al., 2012).
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10 11 **4.4 Limitations and future research**

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14
15 The current research is the first step towards the study of the neural correlates of the
16
17 extrinsic grouping operations. Therefore, some limitations of our experimental
18
19 framework should be considered. Regarding the stimuli, it could be claimed that they
20
21 are simpler than those displayed by previous works studying brain correlates of
22
23 perceptual grouping. Most of these studies made use of larger square lattice displays
24
25 consisting of much more local elements than our stimuli, typically arranged in an 8 x 8-
26
27 matrix (e.g., Han et al., 2001, 2002, 2005a; Seymour et al., 2008). However, it is
28
29 important to note that these studies were not concerned with the study of extrinsic
30
31 grouping cues. In contrast, prior studies displaying common region cues to examine
32
33 grouping competition used similar stimuli to those presented in the current investigation
34
35 (Luna and Montoro, 2011; Montoro and Luna, 2015). A disparity in visual complexity
36
37 could suppose critical differences in the processing resources involved, which may
38
39 stymie a suitable comparison of our data with previous research. Future research on this
40
41 topic should take into account those issues related to the complexity of the stimuli and
42
43 task demands.
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52 Another potential confound may be related to differences in the assignment of response-
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54 keys to the uniform condition (i.e. down arrow key) compared with grouping conditions
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56 (left or right arrow keys). This divergence minimizes the relevance of making a direct
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58 comparison between the behavioural results in the uniform stimuli and the grouping
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1 conditions. However, providing a completely successful solution to this confound does
2
3 not seem possible. In fact, most of the studies have associated a *no go* response with the
4
5 uniform non-grouped stimulus unlike the *go* responses linked to grouped patterns. In
6
7 contrast to the *no go* procedure, we decided to require a *go* response for the uniform
8
9 condition in order to equate the response requirements of the three experimental
10
11 conditions. This is even more important in the case of ERP studies because different
12
13 electrophysiological responses are associated with *no go* and *go* stimuli (larger N2
14
15 and/or P3 amplitudes are typically found in *no go* -response inhibition- relative to *go* -
16
17 response execution- (Albert et al., 2013; Bokura et al., 2001), making difficult to
18
19 disentangle the effects due to perceptual grouping from effects due to other cognitive
20
21 processes. Furthermore, our response procedure allows to achieve a proportional
22
23 distribution of the responses (33% each), preventing distorting effects based on
24
25 expectations about the different probability of events. Another solution to this problem
26
27 could consist in arranging only two responses. For example, Seymour et al. (2008)
28
29 provided the participants with two keys for detecting the presence (or absence) of a
30
31 global pattern whatever their orientation in a square lattice display. However, this latter
32
33 procedure entails displaying a different proportion of trials for each condition (e.g., 50%
34
35 for uniform, 25% for each grouping condition). In the experiments of Ben-Av and Sagi
36
37 (1995), participants had to perform a forced-choice discrimination task indicating the
38
39 horizontal or vertical organization of local elements even in the case of uniform displays
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41 (which were grouped around 50% in each orientation). Unfortunately, this method
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43 makes difficult to accurately discriminate between no grouping and grouping responses.
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55 A different aspect concerns to the use of EEG-based source localization solutions.
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58 Although EEG inverse solutions have been cross-modally validated with studies
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1 combining LORETA and hemodynamic procedures (including fMRI and PET: Dierks
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3 et al., 2000; Mulert et al., 2004; Vitacco et al., 2002), present source localization results
4
5 should be interpreted with caution and require confirmation by further studies using
6
7 fMRI. ERPs are well suited to examine the temporal dynamics of cortical neural
8
9 activity, but their spatial resolution is poorer than other hemodynamic procedures. This
10
11 limitation might be overcome in future studies by using alternative approaches that take
12
13 advantage of simultaneous EEG and fMRI measures. Such a procedure would allow the
14
15 comparison of brain regions and the time-course of their interplay (Mijovic et al., 2012).
16
17 In this sense, the study by Mijovic and colleagues (2014) identified spatiotemporal
18
19 interactions between the different cortical regions involved in contour integration and
20
21 shape detection by applying jointICA to EEG and hemodynamic responses. These
22
23 authors found that a loop from LOC to V1-V2 accounted for ERP effects that emerged
24
25 around 300 milliseconds. This activity was interpreted as an index of the consistency of
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27 the different local elements with the globally defined shape.
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36 Finally, although ERPs have been extensively used to explore the temporal dynamics of
37
38 neural mechanisms, there is recent evidence suggesting that additional sources of
39
40 information may be extracted from recordings of brain electrical activity. In this
41
42 direction, the results of a study by Alexander and colleagues (2013), suggested that
43
44 phase topography and phase gradient, rather than trial average, may be more relevant to
45
46 the understanding of event-related activity. The use of similar methodological
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48 approaches may provide a promising tool for future research in order to further
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50 characterize the neural mechanisms involved in perceptual grouping.
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56 **4.5. Integrating findings and conclusions**

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1 Our results can be interpreted in the context of a comprehensive framework that
2
3 accounts for the temporal course and the anatomical topography of the different neural
4
5 correlates involved in perceptual grouping by common region. Basically, three main
6
7 neural processes related to common region grouping were identified in our analyses (see
8
9 Figure 7).

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14 **[Insert Figure 7 about here]**
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16

17 First, the perceptual operations specifically involved in the processing of visual patterns
18
19 generated by common region cues were indexed by N210 modulations and increased
20
21 activity in BA 19, including the LOC. Inter alia, these operations could be related to the
22
23 perceptual analysis of the extrinsic elements inducing grouping and the formation of a
24
25 visual group that includes the target and other elements based on “similarity of
26
27 containment” (Wagemans et al., 2012). Prior evidence has shown that perceptual choice
28
29 and concomitant confidence emerge along a processing stream in a network of
30
31 secondary sensory cortices and prefrontal areas that are involved in the evaluation and
32
33 monitoring of task difficulty and sensory certainty (Heekeren et al., 2008; Hilgenstock
34
35 et al., 2014; Kiani and Shadlen, 2009). Thus, as a consequence the higher perceptual
36
37 saliency shown by common region cues, the P280 modulation may be reflecting more
38
39 confident decisions about response selection when participants grouped elements in the
40
41 common region condition during a second processing stage. Finally, neural activity in
42
43 the right superior parietal cortex associated with the scalp-recorded P550 component
44
45 seems to be reflecting top-down suppression activity connected with the termination of
46
47 the processing of the current trial. This inhibitory mechanism would facilitate the
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49 resetting of the perceptual system in order to make it ready for the processing of the
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51 next—unpredictable—stimulus.
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1 Palmer (1992, 1999) introduced a distinction between intrinsic and extrinsic grouping
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3 principles. To date, there had been no neural evidence supporting this theoretical
4
5 distinction because the brain mechanisms associated with extrinsic grouping remained
6
7 unexplored. In the current study, we reported for the first time three main ERP effects
8
9 and their neural sources, which were specifically associated with common region
10
11 grouping. Regarding perceptual operations, our results suggest that grouping according
12
13 to common region cues may be included in the category of long latency grouping
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15 principles that mainly involve the activity of extrastriate cortices (Han et al., 2001;
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1 **Figure 1.** All the stimuli displayed in the present study and the correct response for
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3 each one.
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7 **Figure 2.** Timing and sequence of events of an experimental trial.
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10 **Figure 3.** Grand averages at a selection of central and posterior electrode sites, where
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12 the experimental effects (described in the text) are clearly visible.
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15 **Figure 4.** Temporal principal component analysis (tPCA): Temporal factors 5 (N210), 6
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17 (P280), 1 (P470) and 8 (P550) were sensitive to experimental manipulation. TF:
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19 temporal factor.
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24 **Figure 5.** Spatial principal component analysis (sPCA): Spatial decomposition of
25
26 relevant components (N210, P280, P470 and P550). Spatial factors in which statistical
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28 analyses were significant are marked with an asterisk.
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31 **Figure 6.** Main findings of source localization analysis (sLORETA). Top: increased
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33 N210-related activation in the extrastriate visual cortex for common region relative to
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35 no-grouping condition. Bottom: increased P550-related activation for common region
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37 than for no-grouping and luminance conditions. Colour bars represent voxel t values.
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42 Abbreviations: NG, no-grouping; LU, luminance; CR, common region.
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45 **Figure 7.** Illustration of the hypothetical temporal course and cognitive functions of the
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47 neural correlates associated to common region cues.
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Table 2. Scalp ERP results: statistical analyses performed on all temporo-spatial factors extracted by temporo-spatial principal component analysis.

Temporal factor	Spatial factor	ANOVA* ($df = 2, 46$)	Post hoc tests**
TF1 (P470)	Anterior	$F = 2.87, ns$	
	Central	$F = 9.74, p < .05, \eta^2_p = 0.3$	NG > CR NG > LU CR = LU
	Posterior	$F = 5.05, ns$	
TF2	Anterior	$F = 0.12, ns$	
	Central	$F = 1.68, ns$	
	Posterior	$F = 4.32, ns$	
TF3	Anterior	$F = 0.31, ns$	
	Central	$F = 0.19, ns$	
	Posterior	$F = 0.45, ns$	
TF4	Anterior	$F = 2.94, ns$	
	Central	$F = 0.66, ns$	
	Posterior	$F = 0.54, ns$	
TF5 (N210)	Anterior	$F = 1.11, ns$	
	Central	$F = 5.4, ns$	
	Posterior	$F = 20.55, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = 0.5$	CR > LU**** CR > NG**** LU = NG
TF6 (P280)	Anterior	$F = 2.2, ns$	
	Left Posterior	$F = 16.3, p < .001, \eta^2_p = 0.4$	CR > LU CR > NG LU = NG
	Right Posterior	$F = 25.51, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = 0.5$	CR > LU CR > NG LU = NG
TF7	Anterior	$F = 4.04, ns$	
	Left Posterior	$F = 1.83, ns$	

	Right Posterior	$F = 2.17, ns$	
TF8 (P550)	Anterior	$F = 3.96, ns$	
	Central	$F = 9.46, p < .05, \eta^2_p = 0.3$	CR < LU CR < NG LU = NG
	Posterior	$F = 20.42, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = 0.5$	CR < LU CR < NG LU = NG
TF9	Anterior	$F = 5.54, ns$	
	Central	$F = 1.44, ns$	
	Posterior	$F = 3.96, ns$	
TF10	Anterior	$F = 1.94, ns$	
	Left posterior	$F = 1.43, ns$	
	Right Posterior	$F = 2.44, ns$	

Abbreviations: TF: temporal factor; *dg*: degrees of freedom; *ns*, non-significant; CR: common region; LU: luminance similarity; NG: no-grouping.

* Repeated-measure ANOVA with Grouping (three levels: No grouping, Luminance similarity and Common region) as a factor. Given the large number of tests involved ($n = 30$), a Bonferroni correction was used. *P*-values reported in the table are Bonferroni-corrected for multiple comparisons.

** Significant main effects were further decomposed using pairwise comparisons with a Bonferroni correction. Significant results were those with Bonferroni-corrected *p*-values < .05.

*** The posterior N210 showed larger amplitude (more negative, as this component is negative at posterior locations) for common region than for luminance and no-grouping conditions.

Table 3. Source localization results (sLORETA): Significant differences between experimental conditions were found during N210 and P550 time ranges.

Component	Contrast*	<i>t</i> -value of peak voxel	MNI coordinates of peak voxel (x, y, z)	Anatomical region
N210	CR vs. NG	$t = 3.12, p < .05$	-45, -85, 0	Middle occipital gyrus, BA 19
	CR vs. LU	$t = 2.65, p = .1^{\wedge}$	-35, -9, 20	Superior occipital gyrus, BA19
	LU vs. NG	$t = 2.32, ns$		
P550	CR vs. NG	$t = 2.9, p < .05$	5, -50, 70	Post-central gyrus, BA 5
	CR vs. LU	$t = 2.67, p < .05$	10, -55, 70	Post-central gyrus, BA 7
	LU vs. NG	$t = -2.3, ns$		

* The voxel-based whole-brain sLORETA-images (6239 voxels) were compared between conditions by means of the sLORETA built-in voxelwise randomization tests based on statistical non-parametric mapping (SnPM). Therefore, reported *p*-values are corrected for multiple comparisons.

[^] A marginal significance was found between these two conditions.

Abbreviations: *ns*, non-significant; BA, Brodmann Area.

Table 1. Median (SD) RTs (in ms), and mean accuracy (hit rate) for the conditions of the factor Stimulus type.

	No grouping	Luminance similarity	Common region
Reaction time	535 (65.6)	559 (76.7)	501 (64.9)
Accuracy	.98 (0.02)	.94 (0.06)	.98 (0.02)

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